

Investigating Self-concept and Performance of Secondary School Students in Numerical Problems in Physics

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Abstract

The study investigated self-concept and performance of secondary school students in numerical problems in Physics. A correlational design was adopted, where 240 students were randomly selected from a population of 2320 secondary schools from three public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of River State. Two instruments Physics Performance Test (PPT) and a self-structured Self-Concept on Physics Questionnaire (SCPQ). The validated instruments were tested for reliability using test and retest method, and then Pearson Product Moment Reliability Formula (r) was used to obtain 0.72 (PPT) and 0.84 (SCPQ). Then, three correlation tests (Pearson, Kendall's tau_ and Spearman's rho tests) were employed to determine if there is a relationship between students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in Physics. Results of investigation showed a moderate relationship between the students' performance in numerical problems in Physics for School I and II (**0.521, positive**), then a slight relationship between the students' performance in numerical problems in Physics for school I with III (-0.183, negative) and school II with III (0.172, positive). Similarly, there is a positive relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in Physics for School I and School II, while there is a low positive relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in Physics for School III. Hence, there is a low positive relationship between students' self-concept and their performance on numerical problems in Physics. Two tests (Pearson and Spearman's rho correlation) showed the same results of (two fair)/(one slight) relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in Physics, while one test differ (Kendall's tau_ Correlation) showing two slight and one fair relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in Physics. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that Physics teachers should elicit students' self-concepts in order to improve their performances in numerical problems on Physics.

Keywords: *Self-concept, Performance, Numerical problem, Relationship.*

Suggested citation: Avwiri, E., & Biu, E.O. (2026). Investigating Self-concept and Performance of Secondary School Students in Numerical Problems in Physics. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 4(2), 153-161. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2026.4(2).12

Introduction

Self-concept should never be undermined as it takes into account belief about oneself, which goes a long way in influencing the way of life, since it exposes a lot of self-awareness. Students' self-concept is a psychological construct that explains a mental representation made to integrate the experience, feelings, and emotions that it produces. It denotes a sense of physical appearance and physical ability. Self-concept is an innate expression of will and willingness to accept a discovery learning status that annihilates dissatisfaction and unpreparedness towards achieving an expectation or outcome. According to Cherry (2025), self-concept is the personal value, an overall view of the person, who the person is, including the belief, identity abilities which can be improved upon through feedback and self-awareness. It has to do with how much you like and appreciate yourself regardless of the circumstances. Self-concept has a great role in psychological development of an individual and is critical in several areas of personal, social, academic, physical, and emotional development (Ayodele, 2011).

Transitional to specific knowledge in the learning of science subjects are the rudimentary or basic knowledge embedded in pupil's curriculum involving demand for pupils' identification of numbers, division (fractions), science hygiene, prevention, purposes of first aid and scattered reasoning about the natural phenomena of heat, shine and rainfall, they tend to depend on teachers naïve and expositions as dogmatic and authoritative. One of the advantages of these pre-science beliefs and facts is that a pupil's sense of inquiry, self-concept is developing. They also develop interest, emotional control and emotional intelligence which result in modifications, critical thinking, assertiveness and self-concept.

In the specific subjects learning, self-concept relates with students' academic performance in mathematics (Ayodele, 2011). Self-concept tends to produce a commensurate change in academic achievement (Yara, 2010). On Gender relationship with self-concept, Ramesh (2018) reported that the boys seem to have a physical self – concept than the girls.

The build up to self-control or self-esteem is when students are allowed to have control over their acquisition of knowledge. This view has corroborated with the suggestion of Bruner's discovery learning and Gagne hierarchical structure where learning tasks are guided but learner frankly show positive disposition to differentiate preliminary tasks through the process to achieve meaningfully the terminal task. The advocacy for teaching on ways to overcome negative emotions to shape the child's cognitive, emotional, social and physical abilities are within the commonality of learner psychology. Asmara et al. (2025) revealed that self-concept significantly predicts academic performance of students, showing need for academic intervention in teaching and learning process. In line with the view that there is a relationship a positive emotional intelligence in student intelligibility and high academic performance (Prect,

2013; Joibari & Mohammadtaeri, 2011). Also, in the work of Ndungu and Mutweleli (2024) shows a significant relationship between academic self-concept and learners scores on academic achievement.

Mathematics knowledge continues to play vital and conjugate roles in interpretation and presentation of learnable concepts in physics. The thrust of physics learning is to have understanding of the explanations of physical phenomena which are organized in the roots of theories and theoretical models which are useful in the teaching of the subject at all levels. (Aduriz-Bravol, 2012).

Johansson (2013) in the construction of creative reasoning tests in physics, discovered Physics students struggle towards giving explanations to natural phenomena and solving physics problems. The antidote to this problem especially in developing countries are;

1. Encourage students to build a positive resilient self -concept in their academics activities.
2. The teachers should be encouraged to used differentiated instructions such as experimental methods, podcasts, collaborative, guided inquiry and problem solving method.
3. Use of feedback from students after lesson is a good way of to tackle negative self –concept in the students.

However, when students are interested in science and they have good mathematics knowledge, which will help them tackle numerical problems in Physics (Avwiri & Okey, 2023). Physics involve a lot of critical thinking, brainstorming, and understanding of concept with good interpretation of scientific concept. Interestingly, those Math related concepts have been advised to be properly understood, to ease difficulties faced by teachers and students. Other important aspects of the Physics subject such as Wave, Sound, Atomic physics, electronics and wave particle paradox have diversified Math areas.

Most students with poor attitude, avoid, misunderstand and dislike the study of physics for different reasons, this have affected their self-concept negatively and readiness to study, which could lead to poor performance in the subject area. Although Baziliyo and Rajamehala (2022) revealed that time allocation for the science topics taught , the subject teacher teaching load are among some of the factors leading to student's poor performance in Physics. Again, Amadi (2021) emphasized that the unproductive ability of the teacher in the use of instructional material has affected the students' performance negatively. Mathematics' numerous equations , laws and formulas has created phobia for students' numerical problems in physics (Olalekun, et al., 2018). Ogegbo and Ramolarin (2022), suggested the use of interactive simulation: a guided inquiry practice as interventions to scaffold better understanding of concepts despite the difficulties they faced in relating theoretical models to real world phenomena especially using mathematical operations and combining Math operations with conceptual reasoning or about physical phenomena for students during teaching and learning. Research interests increase on how to motivate physics learning and improve performances. If students' self-concept is improved based on teachers' use of core teaching methods and innovation strategies, re-engineering the affective domain and social benefits of the subject matter, identifying their misconceptions and naïve ideas for teaching condition and expertise explanations then, there is a possibility of improving student's self-concept.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the study.

1. How is students' performance in numerical problems in physics?
2. What relationship exists between students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics?

Research Hypothesis

The following null Hypothesis (H_0) are tested at 0.05 significance level.

H_0 : There is no relationship between students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics.

Statement of the Problem

The application of the appropriate teaching method to improve students' performance in school is very crucial. However, there are some key factors which might be a contributing factor to students' high or low performance in physics, there is therefore the need to consider the students' self-concept if it will affect students' performance in numerical problems. The learner's self-concept and determination in the available resources for learning are important to ameliorate the persistence of failure and loss of interest in physics. Numerical problems are built in the concept of Maths - Physics and some students do avoid calculations. Will there be a mutual positive strength inter-relationship between the use of physics - mathematics and how it affects students' performance? Is there a relationship between self-concept and students' performance? The present study would reveal the potency of students' self-concept and performance in numerical problems in physics.

Materials and Methods

The study adopted a correlational research study. According to Castellan (2010), the purpose of correlational research is to discover relationships between /among variable using correlational statistics. The research involved use of correlation design to determine the relationship between self-concepts and students' performance. Two hundred and fifty students randomly selected from a population of 2320 physics students (PPSB, Statistics) in 23 schools in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. Data were collected using a diagnostic scale tool with 20 items in the questionnaire on Self -Concept (QSCP) and 20 item multiple choice test on Physics Performance Test (PPT) on concepts of mechanics, electricity, optics sound and wave particles with reliability of 0.72 and 0.84 estimated using test-retest method and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). A pilot study of the instruments constructed with 20 students in the research area was used to verify the psychomotor properties (validity and reliability). The Self-Concept Questionnaire QSCP was administrated on the participants, retrieved before the PPT for a period of 1hr 30minutes. The collated scores from the participants were used to answer the research questions using mean and standard deviation (SD) for the stated items while the research hypothesis on relationship (r) is tested using PPMC and t-test (t , t).

Results

Research Question 1

How is students' performance in numerical problem in physics?

Table 1. The Average Students' Performance in PPT of the Three Public Secondary Schools

Students' performance in numerical problems in physics	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Students' performance in PPT School I	50.7	16.9709	3.7948
Students' performance in PPT School II	60.9	10.8575	2.4278
Students' performance in PPT School III	68.4	10.3842	2.3220

Table 1 indicates that Students' performance in PPT School III (68.4) have the highest average performance followed by Students' performance in PPT School II (60.9) and Students' performance in PPT School I (50.7) is the least.

Table 1 indicate that students in Group 1, outperformed those in Group II and Group III on numerical problems in physics ($68.4 > 60.9$) followed by students in group I, ($68.4 > 50.7$) and then their counterparts in group II ($60.9 > 50.7$). The average (mean) of 68.4 shows that student's general performance in numerical problems in physics are high in the physics performance test (PPT).

The students' performance in numerical problems in physics were analysis with the help of SPSS and results summarized in Tables 2 and 3 below;

Table 2. The Pearson Correlation Students' Performance in PPT of the Three Public Secondary Schools

Students' Performance in Numerical Problems in Physics	Correlation	p-value (Sig.)
School I - School II	0.521	0.018**
School I - School III	-0.183	0.439
School II - School III	0.172	0.469

Footnote: **=Sig. at 5%

Table 2 showed the Pearson Correlation p-value between School I and II is 0.018, which is significant at the critical level of 5%, while school I and III, school II and III p-values are not significant at 5%.

Table 2: Parametric Test showed where the Pearson Correlation Coefficient was calculated to characterize the students' performance in PPT at $\alpha = 0.05$ level. The comparison was done using the level of reliability of the Pearson correlation. The classification criteria used as reported by Ogoke et al. (2013), Amadi et al., (2020) and Adeyeye & Biu, (2023). These characterizations range from 0.000 to 0.20 (slight), 0.21 to 0.40 (Fair), 0.41 to 0.60 (moderate), 0.61 to 0.80 (substantial) 0.81 to 1.00 (almost perfect).

Table 3. Pearson Correlation level of Reliability of the Students' Performance in PPT among the Three Public Secondary Schools

Students' performance in numerical problems in physics	Pearson Correlation	Level of Reliability
School I - School II	0.521	Moderate (+ve)
School I - School III	-0.183	Slight (-ve)
School II - School III	0.172	Slight (+ve)

Footnote: +ve = positive relationship and -ve = negative relationship

Table 3, there is a moderate relationship between the students' performance in numerical problems in physics for School I and II. There is a slight relationship between the students' performance in numerical problems in physics for school I and III, There is also a slight relationship between the students' performance in numerical problems in Physics for school II and III.

Research Question 2

How does self-concept relate with students' performance in numerical problems in Physics?

Table 4. Summary of Pearson Correlation between Self-Concept and Students' Performance in Numerical Problems in Physics

Students' performance in numerical problems in physics	Pearson Correlation	(p-value)	Level of Reliability
students' self-concept & School I	0.352	(0.128)	Fair (+ve)
students' self-concept & School II	0.372	(0.106)	Fair (+ve)
students' self-concept & School III	0.151	(0.525)	Slight (+ve)

Table 4 shows that there is fair relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics for School I;(35%) for School II (37%) while there is slight relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics for School III (15%). Hence, there is a slight positive relationship between students' self-concept and their performance on numerical problems in physics.

Hypothesis (H₀)

H₀: there is no significant relationship between students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics.

Three correlation tests were employed to determine if there is a relationship between students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in Physics, because the distributions of the two variables differ in terms of count and continuous data. Hence, the correlation tests employed are Pearson, Kendall's tau_ and Spearman's rho, because the data sets are counts and continuous data.

Table 4. Three Correlation Tests between Students' Self-Concept and Students' Performance in Numerical Problems in Physics

Statistics	Students' performance in numerical problems in physics	Correlation	p-value	Level of Reliability
Pearson Correlation	students' self-concept & School I	0.352	(0.128)	Fair (+ve)
	students' self-concept & School II	0.372	(0.106)	Fair (+ve)
	students' self-concept & School III	0.151	(0.525)	Slight (+ve)
Kendall's tau_ Correlation	students' self-concept & School I	0.199	(0.227)	Slight (+ve)
	students' self-concept & School II	0.236	(0.159)	Fair (+ve)
	students' self-concept & School III	0.078	(0.646)	Slight (+ve)
Spearman's rho Correlation	students' self-concept & School I	0.268	(0.254)	Fair (+ve)
	students' self-concept & School II	0.293	(0.209)	Fair (+ve)
	students' self-concept & School III	0.114	(0.631)	Slight (+ve)

The parametric and non-parametric techniques result were summarized in Table 5. From Table 5, there is fair/slight relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics for three Schools considered (i.e. school I II and III), all tests used confirmed it. However, two tests (Pearson and Spearman's rho correlation) showed the same results, while one differ (Kendall's tau_ Correlation).

While there is slight relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics & School III. Hence, there is a fair positive relationship between students' self-concept and their performance on numerical problems in physics.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that there is a moderate relationship between the students' performance in numerical problems in physics for School I and II (0.521, positive), then a slight relationship between the students' performance in numerical problems in physics for school I with III (-0.183, negative) and school II with III (0.172, positive).

Similarly, there is a fair relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics for School I; also for School II, while there is slight relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics & School III. Hence, there is a slight positive relationship between students' self-concept and their performance on numerical problems in physics.

Two tests (Pearson and Spearman's rho correlation) showed the same results of (two fair)/(one slight) relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics, while one test differ (Kendall's tau_ Correlation) showing two slight and one fair relationship between the students' self-concept and their performance in numerical problems in physics. Summarily, the work shows that there is a positive relationship between students' self-concept and their performance. This agrees with the work of Ndungu & Mutweleli (2024) and Asmara et al., (2025) that self -concept significantly predicts academic performance, therefore there is need for academic interventions such as choosing the appropriate instructional methods, motivating, counselling, and close monitoring of students' academic performance and progress.

Conclusion

Physics students' performance in numerical problems depends on their self-concept. Hence, it is suggested that teachers adopt adequate instructional strategy and counseling alternatives in order to improve student's self-concept and performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that;

1. Teachers should elicit and motivate students to improve their self-concept in order to scaffold/improve on their performances in numerical analysis in Physics.
2. Teachers should encourage students towards acquisition of mathematics knowledge in order to improve their performance in numerical problems in Physics.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest in this research.

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